

UNDERSTANDING THE EFFECT OF IN-PLANE FIBER WAVINESS ON DAMAGE BEHAVIOR OF CURED WOVEN COPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

On account of merits such as enhanced fracture toughness and out-of-plane impact resistance due to interlaced fibrous architecture, woven composite materials are gradually being regarded as a superior alternative to unidirectional composites (UDs) in numerous industries. However, the interlaced architecture of fibers leads to complexities such as misalignment and coupling between warp and weft yarns upon the mechanical loading of dry and consolidated woven fabrics. Employing Digital Image Correlation (DIC) and microscopy, this article is an attempt to present a detailed experimental investigation into the mechanical behavior of a consolidated twill woven PP/glass lamina under tensile loading in warp and weft directions so as to assess the unbalancedness effect resulting from in-plane waviness of warp and weft yarns. Results showed that the woven composite specimens under tension in the weft direction behaved linearly up to final failure—analogueous to that of unidirectional composites—whereas they showed a non-linear response with less stiffness under tension in warp direction in the early steps of loading, and subsequently encountered failure modes in ‘multiple’ steps. Moreover, the imaging data revealed that although the induced failure types (matrix cracking followed by fiber fracture) are similar between the warp and weft directions, the source of their failure modes as well as the corresponding stress-strain values are substantially different, even if the fabric would have been initially presumed balanced. The aforementioned observations were further verified via statistical hypothesis testing with $\alpha=5\%$.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the dawn of advanced lightweight structures in aviation, unidirectional (UD) composites have received enormous attention, mainly owing to their high specific stiffness and strength properties as well as simplicity of analysis during sensitive design stages [1-6]. Woven composites, on the other hand, have presented a good alternative to conventional UD composites due to superior mechanical characteristics such as better out-of-plane resistance, less delamination, and ease of moulding processes. These advantageous characteristics arise from the fibrous architecture of woven composites. However, the interlaced fiber architecture also causes complexities during design and analysis of woven fabrics, including inherent in-plane and out-of-plane waviness of yarns, change in the cross-section of yarns along the reinforcement path, and the coupling effect between warp and weft directions [2-6]. Structural complexities of this kind can in turn cause non-linearity in the behavior of woven composites under tensile loading, let alone bending, impact loading and other complex modes such as combined shear-tension loading [7]. As a result, the accurate prediction of mechanical behavior of woven composites is still one of the challenging areas in mechanics of composites. Earlier studies have been carried out at different scales, including micro, meso and macro levels, in order to predict the response of woven fabrics under various loading types. However, on account of some simplifying assumptions in analytical/numerical models [1-6], the above addressed complexities could not be taken into account simultaneously, leading less accurate predictions compared to experimental analyses. Additionally, micro/meso modeling approaches are often time-consuming and not applicable to simulation of large-scale parts. Models at the macro level are computationally less expensive and feasible for analysis of

woven composites at large [8-12]. Most of such models, however, can not consider complexities underlying multi-scale nature of woven fabrics during different deformation and failure modes. In particular, with respect to failure criteria, the phenomenological macro models utilize failure criteria that have been originally proposed for UD composites, with appropriate modifications. Regardless of the modeling scale, experimental analyses continue to bring substantial information to better understanding the response of woven composites under tensile, bending and impact loadings (e.g., [13-16]), while validating the associated prediction models.

The present work is an attempt to understand the effect of in-plane waviness, one of the present complexities in woven composites (Figure 1), upon consolidation and uniaxial extension of a typical 2×2 twill polypropylene/glass prepreg. According to Figure 1, while the weft yarns are commonly straight, the warp yarns are noticeably wavy (misaligned) in the lane of the fabric. There are two types of waviness in woven architectures, the most common of which is ‘out-of-plane’ waviness and inherent to the fiber crimping induced on the loom during weaving. The second type is ‘in-plane’ waviness which is often deemed as random error and may form during weaving or consolidation process. The main goal of this experimental investigation is to show that, statistically, there is significant evidence that the presence of in-plane waviness of warp yarns can present a substantial unbalancedness in the tensile behavior of cured woven laminates, as high as 125%.

Figure 1: Example of in-plane waviness of warp yarns in a woven cured composite (notice that the weft yarns are nearly straight in the plane of fabric)

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Vacuum infusion was employed to manufacture consolidated twill laminas made of commingled PP/glass twill fabrics. The consolidation process was comprised of heating the master plate to 190°C with 15°C/min rate C, holding it at 190°C for 35 min, and cooling to the room temperature. Utilizing water jet, test samples were cut from the plate, following ASTM D3039. According to this standard, the width and gauge length of the samples were selected at 13mm and 150mm, respectively. The average thickness of the fabricated samples was 1.3mm. Tensile tests were conducted using an Instron 5969 equipped with a 50 kN load cell. The rate of elongation was set at 2mm/min to satisfy a quasi-static deformation state. In order to observe the response of twill laminas under each tensile test, the Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique [17] was employed. By associating the force-displacement curves obtained from Instron machine and the continuous images by the DIC, the roots of changes in the force curve slope were explored step-by-step. Although DIC is known to be able to reveal visible damages in composites, it does not enjoy capability to disclose invisible interior damage at micro level. Thus, a ZEISS microscope was employed so as to examine the existence of damage in micro level at different magnitudes of loading, before the visible damage onset captured by DIC. Each tensile test in warp and weft direction was repeated 3 times.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 illustrates typical stress-strain behavior of the twill composite specimens under tensile loading in two directions. According to this figure, the woven composite clearly did not behave similarly in the warp and weft directions, even before damage initiation shown as point A. The main observations from comparison of these two curves and associated image analyses are presented below.

3.1. Before damage initiation

According to Figure 2, the tensile behavior of the weft direction of the samples is almost linear up to the final failure with a sudden drop, which resembles a behavior similar to that of unidirectional composites; while the specimen behaves completely non-linear under the warp direction and then undergoes failure in multiple steps. DIC revealed that these significant differences are on the account of in-plane waviness existence in the warp direction. When tension is applied to the specimen in the weft direction, the loaded yarns, which are nearly straight from the onset, stretch uniformly and result in a linear response. However, when the specimen is subjected to tension in the warp direction, the loaded yarns, which inherently have more in-plane waviness than weft (fill) yarns in the onset (Figure 1), move similar to ‘snake sliding’ on the matrix ground, causing a highly non-linear response as seen in Figure 2.

Additionally, extra specimens were fabricated and subjected to loading up to elongation before the point ‘A’ to examine the existence of potential manufacturing defects inside the samples, by employing a high magnitude microscope. As depicted in Figure 3 (a), the acquired image suggests that there are no pre-induced failure modes before point A in Figure 2. As a result, the non-linear behavior before point ‘A’ was deemed to be merely because of the in-plane waviness effect of the warp direction. It is noteworthy that the out-of-plane waviness in yarns resulting from the weave architecture can only decrease the global stiffness of the composite, causing the fact that the elastic modulus of woven composites is less than unidirectional composites with similar number of yarns in a given direction. However, crimping would not be responsible for the non-linear global behavior of cured woven composite, since the tensile behavior of the tested specimen in weft direction is still linear up to the failure with a sharp fall afterward. In fact it is the in-plane waviness of warp yarns that has reduced the global stiffness of the material and caused non-linearity in the material response in that direction.

Figure 2: A comparison between the stress-strain behavior of the cured PP/glass twill lamina in the warp and weft directions

Figure 3: (a) Perfect bonding between yarns and matrix before matrix cracking point in Figure 2, (b) Debonding between warp yarns and matrix 'after' the matrix cracking point

3.2. Matrix cracking

In addition to the influence of the wavy fiber geometry on the non-linearity in the early steps of loading, the higher in-plane waviness of yarns accelerated the matrix cracking in the specimen under warp tension. DIC clearly showed that during loading in this direction, the warp yarns force the matrix accompany the loaded yarns. However, the matrix can resist such movement up to a certain extent, thereafter the matrix cracking arises and it is de-bonded from yarns, as shown in Figure 3(b). In turn the matrix cracking makes the material integrity discontinued, and hence decreasing the global stiffness of the specimen and causing a noticeable change in the slope of stress-strain curve after point A in Figure 2. On the other hand, when the weft yarns were subjected to the same tensile loading, because they have less in-plane waviness, the matrix and loaded yarns were stretched more uniformly with each other and, hence, the matrix cracking was developed very close to the ultimate tensile failure.

In order to perform further investigation into the angle of matrix cracks in the tested woven composite samples, real-time images obtained by DIC were post-processed more closely. Results clarified that the matrix cracking happens in 45° angle with respect to the loading direction, as illustrated in Figure 4. Essentially, the matrix locations surrounding wavy warp yarns (red regions in Figure 5) would be most vulnerable to matrix cracking. This fact could be further interpreted by observed local deformation fields through DIC images. DIC demonstrated that parts of the warp yarns adjacent to the red regions have higher magnitudes of deformation, considering both longitudinal and transverse directions. Moreover, microscope images of the specimens subjected to tension up to an elongation between points A and B in Figure 2 (i.e., after matrix cracking and before the final failure) illustrated the failure between yarns and matrix interface (Figure 3 (b)). This figure also reconfirms that the matrix cracking has occurred in 45° with respect to the loading direction, implying that shear failure has happened in the PP matrix. At the macro-level, the latter point was also proven through two other means. The first evidence is illustrated in Figure 6. This figure shows that the longitudinal axes of the two separated parts of the ruptured specimen under warp tension are not aligned with one another (the angle between them is approximately 135°). It means that the warp-tensioned specimens, next to fiber tension, experience some shear deformation owing to the in-plane waviness of fibers. Such coupled behavior between shear deformation and tensile loading had been earlier reported in experiments on 'dry' woven fabric composites [18]. The current results confirm that in the 'cured' woven composites, the in-plane waviness of yarns can also result in shear deformation while off-axis tension is applied on the specimen. Another important point can be deduced from Figure 7. The global tearing direction in the specimen subjected to the tensile loading in warp direction is approximately 45° , whereas the specimen under weft tension tears at a direction perpendicular to loading, similar to a unidirectional composite.

Figure 4: Different steps of mechanical behavior of twill composite specimen under warp tension (the white region in the red ellipse of Figure 4 (b) which does not exist in Figure 4 (a) shows matrix crack in macro level)

Figure 5: Schematic of susceptible regions to undergo failure in a wavy fiber yarn, consolidated with matrix, and loaded axially; red regions: matrix cracking; blue regions: fiber fracture

Figure 6: A comparison between cross-sections of the twill samples after final breakage: (a) tensile loading in the warp direction, and (b) tensile loading in the weft direction

Figure 7: A close-up image of the breakage angles at the tested twill samples: (a) tensile loading in the warp direction, and (b) tensile loading in the weft direction

3.3. Ultimate failure

Figure 2 evinces that although the two groups of twill woven specimens under tension have faced matrix cracking, followed by fiber fracture, the ultimate strength and ultimate elongation values are quite different between the two warp and weft groups. This fact is again owing to the in-plane waviness of warp yarns which leads to a decrease in the global stiffness of the material from the onset of loading, as well as accelerated matrix cracking through shear mechanism as discussed in Section 3.2, both of which considerably reducing the ultimate ‘tensile’ strength. Through artificially induced different waviness amplitudes, the earlier study [19] reported a similar observation on the reduction of ‘compressive’ strength in woven samples. They also found that the magnitude of the strength reduction is linearly proportional to the waviness severity. Regarding ultimate elongation, as shown in Figure 2, the twill specimen under warp tension is able to withstand more stretch before failure point. To explain, when the tension is applied in warp direction, part of the specimen elongation is to straighten the curvy yarns and the other part is on account of fibers stretching. On the other hand, tensile behavior of the weft yarns comprises stretching from early stages of material elongation. As a consequence, the total elongation of the woven composite under warp direction is greater in comparison to that of weft direction.

4. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF TEST DATA

In order to objectively assess the effect of in-plane waviness on the mechanical behavior of tested woven composites under tensile loading, statistical analysis was carried out. Namely, Student’s t-test with equal variance assumption was exploited to reveal the difference between mechanical properties of the two main directions of the woven composite. Table 1 presents the experimental data under tensile loading in both warp and weft directions. The statistical analysis results are summarized in Table 2 and convey that the P-values for all the properties measured in Table 1 are less than the significance level (5%). Hence, it can be said that, statically, there is a significant effect of architectural unbalancedness in the twill woven composite on the material tensile behavior. Furthermore, another t-test was employed to examine the validity of shear failure hypothesis in the matrix, when the specimen is subjected to tension in warp direction. Considering the matrix as an isotropic material, the corresponding null hypothesis defined for this t-test was that, the elongation at matrix cracking in warp direction is half of that in weft direction. The obtained P-value was 40%, suggesting the null hypothesis could not be rejected and confirming the presence of shear in warp tensioned cured woven samples.

Loading direction (Treatment)	Replication#	Effective Young's modulus (Gpa)	Elongation at matrix crack initiation (%)	Ultimate strength (Mpa)	Ultimate strain (%)
Warp direction (yarns with in-plane waviness)	1	2.8	1.9	75.18	3.94
	2	2.97	1.72	80.44	4.6
	3	2.78	2.35	83.72	4.46
Weft direction (yarns with no in-plane waviness)	1	4.96	3.6	184.37	3.79
	2	4.75	3.61	172	3.64
	3	4.79	3.67	175.5	3.7

Table 1: Comparison between experimental results of tensile loading on the woven composites in warp and weft directions

Material property	Average value in warp direction	Average value in weft direction	P-value
Effective Young's modulus(Gpa)	2.85	4.83	0.00002
Elongation at matrix crack initiation (%)	1.99	3.62	0.00009
Ultimate strength (Mpa)	79.78	179.29	0.00003
Ultimate strain (%)	4.33	3.71	0.03

Table 2: Statistical results of mechanical properties of the woven composites using Student's t-test

5. CONCLUSION

This work undertook tensile tests on consolidated PP/glass twill woven composite samples in both warp and weft directions, in order to explore the effect of in-plane waviness of fibers, as one of the main complexities in woven composites arising from weaving and/or consolidation process. In most fabrics, especially those with less fiber density, warp yarns often have in-plane as well as out-of-plane waviness, whereas the weft yarns mainly exhibit out-of-plane waviness (fiber crimping). Digital Image Correlation and microscopy were employed to acquire visual knowledge on the influence of in-plane fiber waviness on mechanical properties and damage mechanism of the tested woven composite. The results clearly demonstrated that, not only in-plane waviness causes a non-linear global response in the material with less effective stiffness, it also accelerates the failure modes in the composite. Twill specimens under warp tension, in which in-plane waviness existed, behaved non-linearly while encountering damage in multiple steps. On the other hand, a fairly linear stress-strain response up to the final failure was observed in tensile tests in weft direction, similar to UD composites. DIC and microscopy were highly instrumental to understand that although the above geometrical unbalancedness cannot affect the type of failure modes, their reason and onset can be notably different in warp and weft tensile samples. Namely, while matrix experienced cracks due to shear failure under warp tension, the tensile strain failure was the main reason of matrix cracking when the specimens exposed to loading in the weft direction. In summary, complexities resulting from the unbalanced nature of the interlacing weft and warp yarns, along with associated matrix cracking onsets, can lead to statistically significant differences between the warp and weft material properties such as stiffness, elongation at damage initiation, ultimate stress, and ultimate strain. Practically, fully balanced properties should not be assumed for as-received woven fabrics, even with identical fiber content in the two directions. Fabrics with least warp 'in-plane waviness' should be preferred in order to justify such an assumption; otherwise the reinforcement should be treated mechanically and statistically as unbalanced.

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